

Magnetic and Spectral Studies on Some Transition Metal Chelates of 3-Nitroso-4-Hydroxy-5, 6-Benzocoumarin

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3-Nitroso-4-hydroxy-5,6-benzocoumarin forms a 1:3 (metal:ligand) complex with cobalt(III) and 1:2 (metal:ligand) complexes with nickel(II), copper(II) and palladium(II). Complexes of cobalt(III) and palladium(II) are diamagnetic and those of nickel(II) and copper(II) paramagnetic (μ_{eff} 3.10 B.M. and 1.95 B.M. respectively). Electronic spectra of the complexes have been described and discussed. Mode of coordination of the ligand has been inferred from the infrared spectra.

WE have recently reported¹⁻⁴ the preparation of 3-nitroso-4-hydroxy-5,6-benzocoumarin (NHBC) and its use as an analytical reagent for some transition metal ions. The present communication describes preparation of NHBC complexes of cobalt(III), nickel(II), copper(II) and palladium(II) and their characterization by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility measurements and ultraviolet, visible and infrared spectral studies.

Experimental

(a) Preparation of the complexes:

(i) *Cobalt(III)-NHBC complex*: Acetonic solution of NHBC (80 ml, 0.2M) was added to an equimolar solution of cobalt acetate (20 ml). An orange-red complex immediately precipitated out. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, ethanol and dried at 60° in an electric oven; m.p. 250°(d). The complex is insoluble in water and ethanol and soluble in chloroform, benzene and dimethyl formamide.

(ii) *Nickel(II)-NHBC complex*: An acetonic solution of NHBC (40 ml, 0.1M) was added to an equimolar solution of nickel acetate (20 ml) and pH of the solution was raised to 5.0 with the help of sodium hydroxide solution, when a dark yellowish-brown colouration was obtained. The contents were refluxed for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. On concentrating over a boiling water bath, a dark yellow-brown complex precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and 10% acetone and dried at 60° in an electrically heated oven; m.p. 265°(d). The complex is insoluble in water and soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, chloroform and dimethyl formamide.

(iii) *Copper(II)-NHBC complex*: Acetonic solution of NHBC (40 ml, 0.1M) was added to an equimolar aqueous solution of copper acetate (20 ml). On adding sodium hydroxide solution to raise pH to 7.0, a brown coloured complex precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and acetone and

dried at 60° in an electrically heated oven. The complex is insoluble in water, ethanol and acetone, slightly soluble in 1:4 dioxane and fairly soluble in dimethyl formamide.

(iv) *Palladium(II)-NHBC complex*: Acetonic solution of NHBC (45 ml, 0.1M) was added to an equimolar solution of palladium(II) chloride (20 ml). On adding sodium hydroxide, to raise the pH, a brownish-black complex precipitated at pH 4.0. It was filtered, washed with water and acetone and dried at 60° in an electrically heated oven. The complex is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, benzene and chloroform and slightly soluble in 1:4 dioxane and dimethyl formamide.

(b) Physical measurements:

Magnetic susceptibility measurements on solid complexes were made by Gouy method, using mercury(II)-tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units) as calibrating agent. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in nujol mull on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord-137, in the range 700-4000 cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra of the complexes (in dimethyl formamide, 300-700 $\text{m}\mu$) were recorded on Beckman DU-2(manual) spectrophotometer. Spectra of nickel(II) complex was also recorded in the range 700-1200 $\text{m}\mu$ in methanol.

Results and Discussion

Results of elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility, ultraviolet, visible and infrared spectral data have been presented in Table I. 3-Nitroso-4-hydroxy-5,6-benzocoumarin(I) molecule contains nitroso and phenolic groups in ortho position, ideally situated for forming six membered metal chelate ring(II).

N = O stretching frequency is assigned⁵ to a strong band appearing at 1600 cm^{-1} . Position of this band is shifted towards lower wave numbers (cobalt complex 1570 cm^{-1} , nickel complex 1575 cm^{-1} , copper

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS

Compounds*	Calculated				Found				Magnetic moments	Electronic absorption bands (cm ⁻¹)	I.R. bands (cm ⁻¹)	
	%C	%H	%M	%N	%C	%H	%M	%N			C-O	N=O
Co(L) ₃	60.08	2.31	7.50	5.38	59.95	2.18	7.25	5.20	Diamagnetic	22700	1320	1570
Ni(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	54.26	2.78	10.26	4.87	54.08	2.72	10.02	4.59	3.10 B.M.	11000, 18000 17000	1320	1575
Cu(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	50.69	3.25	10.32	4.55	49.74	3.05	10.20	4.21	1.95 B.M.	21950, 28000, 16100	1325	1570
Pd(L) ₂	53.24	2.05	18.28	4.77	51.58	1.96	18.05	4.37	Diamagnetic	22200, 26800, 28200, 30500	1300	1560
LH (ligand)	64.73	2.90	—	5.80	64.50	2.78	—	5.68	—	—	1340	1600

*L Stands for deprotonated ligand

complex 1570 cm⁻¹ and palladium complex 1560 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes. This indicates coordination through the nitrosyl oxygen. In the O-H stretching frequency region⁶, a band at 3500 cm⁻¹ is observed. However, this region of the i.r. spectrum is of limited value in diagnosis as similar vibrations for water molecules are bound to interfere. Positive evidence for release of phenolic hydrogen on complex formation is provided by pH-metric titrations, where release of proton on adding metal ion solution to the ligand solution is evidenced.

Cobalt-NHBC complex is diamagnetic and an octahedral stereochemistry around the cobalt(III) ion is indicated. While cobalt(II) was used for the preparation of the complex, aerial oxidation appears to have caused the valence change, as is usually observed. Visible spectra of the regular octahedral cobalt(III) complexes are known⁷ to exhibit usually two absorption bands owing to the transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$. The electronic spectrum of the complex under study contains a broad charge transfer band at 440 m μ , (22,700 cm⁻¹, $\epsilon = 19,500$) extending between 350 m μ –600 m μ). This evidently prevents the appearance of the above mentioned d-d bands.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements on the nickel(II)-NHBC complex yield a magnetic moment value of 3.10 B.M. The square-planar stereochemistry is therefore excluded from consideration. For a choice between octahedral and tetrahedral stereochemistry, the electronic spectrum of the complex has to be considered. The electronic spectrum of the complex under study shows absorption bands at 27,000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 24,225$), 18,000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon \approx 500$) and 11,000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon \approx 300$). The bands at 11,000 cm⁻¹ and 18,000 cm⁻¹ are assignable¹⁶⁻¹⁸ to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2), arising in octahedral nickel(II) complexes. The high intensities may be because of borrowing mechanism or purely because of the extension of the tail of a near ultraviolet absorption into the visible region. The band at 27,000 cm⁻¹ appears, however, to be a charge-transfer band.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements on the copper(II)-NHBC complex yield a magnetic moment value of 1.95 B.M., indicating mononuclear nature of complex⁸. The electronic spectrum of the complex contains three absorption bands 21,950 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 2190$), 28,000 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 12,600$) and 16,100 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 292$). While first two bands are evidently due to charge transfer, the third one may be a d-d band.

Palladium(II)-NHBC complex is diamagnetic in nature. Square planar complexes of d⁸ configuration are of the spin-paired type¹⁰. The electronic spectra of the diamagnetic square planar complexes of d⁸ configuration are expected to contain bands corresponding to the four types of the transitions¹¹; d $\rightarrow$ d, L $\rightarrow$ M, M $\rightarrow$ L and L $\rightarrow$ L*. The electronic spectrum of the complex under study contains absorption bands at 22,200 cm⁻¹, 26,800 cm⁻¹, 28,000 cm⁻¹ and 30,500 cm⁻¹. The first two bands may be

assigned¹²⁻¹⁵ to d-d transitions, while the later two seem to be charge transfer bands.

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